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Bridging the gaps in EU aquaculture: Building resilience in Manila clam farming

Climate change is reshaping European aquaculture at an unprecedented pace. Marine heatwaves are increasing in frequency and intensity, and rising temperatures favour the emergence and spread of pathogens. For bivalve farming systems, where animals are entirely at the mercy of surrounding environmental conditions, these pressures can rapidly translate into mortality events and production instability.

Unlike finfish aquaculture, shellfish farming offers limited opportunities for intervention once stress and disease events occur. Consequently, improving the resilience and adaptive capacity of farmed bivalve stocks through selective breeding is increasingly viewed as a strategic priority for sustainable production. However, the implementation of structured breeding programmes in European clam aquaculture has

long been constrained by the lack of dedicated genomic tools. The Horizon Europe funded project “IGNITION” was designed to address this gap by developing practical genomic solutions tailored to European clam species.

A genomic platform for European clams

A major outcome of the IGNITION project is the development of the first dual-species single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) array specifically designed for European clam aquaculture. The platform includes 63,585 genomic markers, comprising 49,392 markers for the Manila clam (*Ruditapes philippinarum*) and 14,193 markers for the native grooved carpet shell (*Ruditapes decussatus*).

Geographic sampling and SNP array composition for Manila Clam and Grooved Carpet shell.

Credit: Science Crunchers

Clam genotyping infographic. Credit: Science Crunchers

Developed using multiple European populations, the array was designed to capture the genetic diversity present across farming regions, ensuring applicability to both hatchery stocks and natural populations. For the first time, clam producers and researchers have access to a standardized genomic tool capable of supporting pedigree reconstruction, estimation of genetic parameters, and large-scale genotyping. Importantly, the platform has already moved beyond research development and is now commercially available, marking a transition from experimental genomics to operational infrastructure for the aquaculture sector.

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From tool development to real-world testing

To demonstrate its practical applicability, the SNP array was immediately deployed within large-scale resilience experiments conducted as part of the IGNITION project. In collaboration with the SATMAR hatchery, a controlled cross involving 15 sires and 50 dams generated an F1 Manila clam population. Approximately 1,000 individuals were exposed to a simulated marine heatwave under laboratory conditions. Following acclimation, animals

experienced daily temperatures ranging from 31°C to 35°C for 16 days, mimicking extreme thermal events recently observed in the Venice Lagoon, one of the most important production areas in Europe.

A second cohort of F1 clams was transferred to field conditions in the Venice Lagoon to evaluate resistance to the protozoan parasite *Perkinsus olseni* under natural exposure. Infection prevalence was monitored monthly, and once infection levels exceeded 40%, approximately 1,000 individuals were sampled and analysed for infestation intensity.

Across both experimental challenges, around 2,000 clams were genotyped using the newly developed SNP array, linking survival, growth performance, and infection data with genome-wide genetic information. The successful application of the platform under both laboratory and field conditions confirmed its practical robustness and suitability for large-scale breeding applications.

Although analyses are still ongoing, preliminary observations suggest the presence of heritable variation for several traits of commercial and adaptive relevance, including growth performance, resistance to *Perkinsus* infection, and tolerance to heat stress. These early indications highlight the potential for selective breeding approaches to contribute to improved resilience in European Manila clam aquaculture.

From research to sector adoption

Climatic conditions mean that European clam aquaculture is increasingly transitioning toward hatchery-based seed supply, creating favourable conditions for systematic genetic improvement. The availability of a validated SNP array tailored to European populations provides the genomic foundation needed to support future breeding initiatives aimed at enhancing both productivity and resilience. The platform has already attracted interest beyond the research community. Industrial partners are promoting the SNP array through their communication channels, and the tool has been presented at scientific and sector-focused conferences. Several research institutions and commercial hatcheries have expressed interest in adopting the platform, highlighting growing recognition of genomics as a practical component of modern shellfish aquaculture.

By combining large-scale challenge experiments with a practical genomic tool, the IGNITION project provides European clam aquaculture with the foundations needed to progressively integrate genetic improvement into routine production systems.

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Since 1976, EAS has been bringing people together for the sustainable development of European aquaculture. As we celebrate our 50th birthday, we look back on key moments and key persons that made EAS what it is today. And we also look forward - continuing to expand our student activities and network and propose benefits for members that are suited to their profile and needs. We will celebrate this milestone throughout the year on social media, and in person at Aquaculture Europe 2026 in Ljubljana, where we invite EAS members to join the celebrations.

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